

SUPER CONDUCTIVE OXIDE LAYERS

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Abstract: *The increase in the world's population and the change in ecology will lead to an increase in the demand for renewable energy sources. The role of solar photovoltaic cells is incomparable in the continuous delivery of cheap and environmentally friendly energy to the population. To come up with ways to increase the efficiency and usability of small-sized solar photovoltaic cells and to take measures to apply them to everyday life. In the process of preparing a solar photocell, coating using different methods of coating and checking their electrophysical and optical properties by taking photocells of different composition in vacuum setups.*

Keywords: *Solar photovoltaic, thin film materials, semiconducting metal oxides, polymers, carbon structures with high electrical conductivity and good optical transparency*

Humanity uses almost exclusively solar energy in all its creative activities. Solar energy is stored in oil, coal, gas, wood, wind and falling water. In the next period, the direct use of solar energy is gaining momentum, and this direction has practically unlimited possibilities. Therefore, it is useful to get acquainted with the most necessary information about the sun itself and its radiation. The role of solar photovoltaic cells is incomparable in the continuous delivery of cheap and environmentally friendly energy to the population.

Zinc oxide is a popular and long-known compound widely used in various

fields of industrial technology and medicine. ZnO thin films are weather resistant and chemically inert, transparent in the visible and infrared regions of the spectrum. They are used as electrical contacts, reflective coatings for thin-film solar cells, and touch displays.

At this point, we will first stop with the concepts we know about oxides. Oxides are compounds of elements with oxygen. In a normal oxide molecule, all oxygen atoms are bonded only to atoms of that element, but not to each other. In the composition of peroxide, superoxide and ozonides (peroxide and peroxide compounds), oxygen atoms are not attached to atoms of elements, but also to each other (for example, SnO_2 - normal oxide, VaO_2 - peroxide). Normal oxides are formed from the direct combination of elements with oxygen, hydroxides of elements are formed from the separation of salts of carbonate, nitrate, sulfate and other oxygen acids.

Oxides are named as follows: a) if an element forms only 1 oxygen compound with oxygen, it is called an oxide. For example, Al_2O_3 is aluminum oxide, MgO is magnesium oxide; b) if several oxides of the element are known, its oxidation state is taken into account: Si_2O copper (oxide, SiO - copper (P)-oxide, Sg_2O_3 - chromium (S)-oxide, SgO_3 - chromium (VI)-oxide and hakazo) of the element if the oxide turns into an acid under the influence of water (or can be obtained from an acid or its salt), the same oxide is called an anhydride of that acid: SO_j - sulfate anhydride, SO_2 - sulfite anhydride [1].

Normal oxides are divided into 3 groups: basic, acidic and amphoteric (intermediate) oxides. In Mendeleev's periodic system, going from left to right in the period, the properties of the oxide change from basicity to amphotericity, and then to acidity. For example, from oxides of period III elements Na_2O , MgO -based oxide Al_2O_3 amphoteric oxide; SiO_2 , P_2O_5 , SO_3 and S_2O_7 are acidic oxides. As the oxidation level of the element increases, the basic properties of oxides become weaker: MgO has a basic property, $\text{Mg}^{>2}$ has an amphoteric

property, Mp_2O_7 has an acid property [2].

Since some oxides do not form salts, they are called indifferent oxides (for example, SO and NO). Most oxides are found in nature. One of the most common oxides in nature is water - hydrogen oxide. Silicate anhydride (SiO_2) is a component of many rocks. Oxides are widely used in life and technology. For example, slaked lime CaO is used in construction, NO_2 , SO_2 - nitric and sulfuric acid, and mixtures consisting of oxides of some metals are used as catalysts [3].

Oxidation (German Oxydierung) is a method of protecting or beautifying the surface of metal objects from corrosion by chemically and electrochemically heating in air with the help of oxidizing solutions. The most common types of chemical oxidation are alkaline and non-alkaline oxidation. In alkaline oxidation, the product is passed through a medium of boiling sodium or potassium alkali solution. In non-alkaline oxidation, the product is oxidized by heating it in a mixture of phosphoric acid, potassium or barium nitrate and manganese phosphate at a temperature of 100° . During chemical oxidation, a 3x oxide layer is formed on the surface of the product. After this layer is coated or lubricated, the metal is more resistant to corrosion. These methods are used for oxidation of steel, cast iron and zinc products. Electro-chemical oxidation (anodization) is carried out under the influence of current. This method gives better results than chemical oxidation. For example, 20% sulfuric acid heated to 30° for 20-60 minutes (current 1.5-2.5 A and voltage 10-20 V) is oxidized with a current, an oxide film 20 nm thick is formed on the surface of the product. The surface of the oxidized product is lacquered. In anodizing, the thickness of the oxide layer can be reached up to 600 nm. This method is mainly used for oxidation of aluminum copper and other metal alloys.

Transparent superconducting coatings (TCO) are various thin film materials: semiconducting metal oxides, polymers, carbon structures with high electrical conductivity and good optical transparency. Metal oxide-based TCO has received

the largest application today. Most of them are binary compounds containing one metallic element: tin oxide (SnO_2), indium oxide (In_2O_3) and zinc oxide (ZnO).

Table 1 shows their main electrical properties [4].

Table 1 - Main characteristics of transparent conductive pure metal oxides

Metals	Band width, eV	Conduction gap, cm/cm	Electron concentration, cm-3	Mobility gap, cm ² /(vs)
SnO_2	3,60	5000	>1020	15
In_2O_3	3,75	10000	>1021	35
ZnO	3,35	8000	>1021	20

In the stoichiometric composition, the compounds are insulators, but due to the large number of internal defects (oxygen vacancies and interstitial metal atoms), they can become semiconductors with a wide bandgap $E_g > 3$ eV. The energy of formation of defects (oxygen vacancies and interstitial atoms) is very low, so these defects are easily formed, which explains the relatively low resistance of non-stoichiometric metal oxides [5]. In order for TCO films to be transparent and have high conductivity, the band gap should exceed 3 eV, free charge carriers should have low effective mass m^* and high mobility.

Various deposition methods are used to obtain films of transparent conducting oxides: magnetron sputtering, continuous wave discharge ion sputtering, high frequency ion sputtering, ion beam sputtering, ion deposition, sputtering after pyrolysis, Examples include chemical vapor deposition, electron-beam, gas-phase deposition, sol-gel method, layer-by-layer atomic deposition, and others.

CONCLUSION

In the production of superconducting oxide layer, coating methods and their effect on optical, electrical and structural properties are considered. As shown, the most promising methods for industrial production of TCO (Transparent conductive oxide) are thermal evaporation and magnetron sputtering. The methods of comparing TCO (Transparent conductive oxide) consisting of different materials used by different methods have been selected. To process the results of optical measurements, the methods of determining the main properties of TCO (Transparent conductive oxide) from the measured spectra are considered: transmission, band gap, possible type of interband electronic transition , electron mobility or concentration. Algorithms are developed for this, and the corresponding software is created. Oxide and fluoride composite materials are synthesized and analyzed in a solar furnace for the use of transparent and electrically conductive coatings.

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